

Divisibility of the digit-reversal difference

(the mirror-number theorem)

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Abstract

We prove that, in any positional base $b \geq 2$, the absolute difference between a natural number and its *reversal* (the number obtained by reversing the order of its digits) is always divisible by $b - 1$; in particular, in base ten, it is always divisible by 9. The main proof presented here is the author's original one, based on the digit-sum rule (*casting out nines*); a structural form is also given, exhibiting the contribution of each pair of symmetric digits. The result is a classical fact of elementary number theory, closely tied to the divisibility-by-nine criterion; this note is a self-contained exposition with an original proof.

1 Definitions and notation

Definition (Reversal of a number). Let $b \geq 2$ be an integer, the *base*. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ with base- b representation

$$n = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} a_i b^i, \quad a_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, b-1\}, \quad a_{L-1} \neq 0,$$

where L is the number of digits, the *reversal* (or *mirror*) of n is

$$\text{rev}_b(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} a_i b^{L-1-i}.$$

In base ten we simply write $\text{rev}(n)$.

For instance $\text{rev}(12) = 21$ and $\text{rev}(42) = 24$.

2 The theorem

Theorem (Divisibility of the reversal difference). For every base $b \geq 2$ and every $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$(b-1) \mid |n - \text{rev}_b(n)|.$$

In particular, in base ten, 9 divides $|n - \text{rev}(n)|$ for every natural number n . The constant $b - 1$ is optimal: no larger integer divides the difference for all n .

The proof relies on the following classical fact.

Lemma (Casting out nines). The digit sum of a number is congruent to the number itself modulo 9; iterating the digit sum down to a single digit yields the remainder of the division by 9 (with the convention that multiples of 9 give 9 instead of 0).

Proof. Since $10 \equiv 1 \pmod{9}$, we have $10^k \equiv 1 \pmod{9}$ for every $k \geq 0$. Hence, for $n = \sum_i c_i 10^i$,

$$n = \sum_i c_i 10^i \equiv \sum_i c_i \pmod{9},$$

i.e. n is congruent modulo 9 to the sum of its digits. □

Author's original proof (18 May 2003, 9:42 a.m.) Let $a \in \mathbb{N}$ be the chosen number, $a' = \text{rev}(a)$ its reversal, and $b = a - a'$. Denote by R_a and $R_{a'}$ the digit sums of a and a' respectively.

1) By the Lemma, $a \equiv R_a \pmod{9}$ and $a' \equiv R_{a'} \pmod{9}$.

2) The reversal a' has the same digits as a , merely reordered; their sum is therefore the same, i.e. $R_a = R_{a'}$.

3) Subtracting the two congruences of step 1) term by term (a legitimate operation between congruences of equal modulus),

$$b = a - a' \equiv R_a - R_{a'} \pmod{9}.$$

4) But by step 2) $R_a = R_{a'}$, so $R_a - R_{a'} = 0$ and therefore

$$b \equiv 0 \pmod{9},$$

that is $9 \mid b$. Since $9 \mid b$ if and only if $9 \mid |b|$, the claim holds for the absolute difference as well. \square

Optimality of the constant. For $n = b$ (i.e. "10" in base b) we have $\text{rev}_b(b) = 1$ and hence $n - \text{rev}_b(n) = b - 1$; thus the greatest common divisor of all differences is exactly $b - 1$, and in base ten exactly 9.

3 Structural form

The same conclusion admits an equivalent form that makes visible the contribution of each pair of symmetric digits.

Proposition (Contribution per symmetric pair). *With the notation of the Definition,*

$$n - \text{rev}_b(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor L/2 \rfloor - 1} (a_{L-1-i} - a_i) b^i (b^{L-1-2i} - 1),$$

and each summand is a multiple of $b - 1$, since

$$b^m - 1 = (b - 1)(b^{m-1} + b^{m-2} + \dots + 1).$$

If L is odd, the central digit (index $i = (L - 1)/2$) gives a null contribution, being fixed by the reversal.

Proof. We have $n - \text{rev}_b(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} a_i (b^i - b^{L-1-i})$. Pairing the indices i and $L - 1 - i$ with $i < L - 1 - i$,

$$a_i (b^i - b^{L-1-i}) + a_{L-1-i} (b^{L-1-i} - b^i) = (a_{L-1-i} - a_i) (b^{L-1-i} - b^i),$$

and $b^{L-1-i} - b^i = b^i (b^{L-1-2i} - 1)$. The factorization of $b^m - 1$ shows that each term is a multiple of $b - 1$. \square

Example. For $n = 1977$ (base ten): the outer pair (1,7) contributes $(1 - 7) \cdot 999 = -5994 = 9 \cdot (-666)$; the inner pair (9,7) contributes $(9 - 7) \cdot 90 = 180 = 9 \cdot 20$. Their sum is $-5814 = 9 \cdot (-646) = 1977 - 7791$.

4 Corollary and remarks

Corollary. *In base ten, every difference $|n - \text{rev}(n)|$ is a multiple of 9; for palindromes it equals 0, itself a multiple of 9.*

Remark.

- (i) The result is equivalent to the fact that n and $\text{rev}_b(n)$ share the same remainder modulo $b - 1$, having the same digit sum: this is the classical *casting out nines*.
- (ii) If n ends in zeros, $\text{rev}_b(n)$ has leading zeros and hence fewer significant digits; the theorem still holds (e.g. $100 - 1 = 99$).
- (iii) The map rev_b is an involution on the naturals without trailing zeros: $\text{rev}_b(\text{rev}_b(n)) = n$.

References

- [1] G. H. Hardy, E. M. Wright, *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers*, Oxford University Press (divisibility criteria and congruences modulo nine).